

TYPES OF ENGINEERING STRUCTURES AND THEIR GEOMETRIC
SHAPE, SIZE, AND CONSTRUCTIVE SPECIFICITY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6066754>

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Abstract: *The development of the economy of any state depends on the moderate functioning of the various enterprises and organizations on which it is based. Existing enterprises and organizations require constant expansion, new facilities are designed and built. Geodesists classify engineering structures according to their geometric shape, size, and structural features.*

Аннотация: *Развитие экономики любого государства зависит от умеренного функционирования различных предприятий и организаций, на которых она основана. Существующие предприятия и организации требуют постоянного расширения, проектируются и строятся новые объекты. Геодезисты классифицируют инженерные сооружения по их геометрической форме, размеру и конструктивным особенностям.*

Аннотация: *Хар қандай давлат иқтисодиётининг ривожланиши, унинг негизда мавжуд бўлган турли хил корхона ва ташиқлотларнинг ўзаро боғлиқ равишида мўътадил фаолият юритишига боғлиқ. Мавжуд корхона ва ташиқлотлар доимий кенгайтиришни талаб этади, янги объектлар лойиҳаланади ва қурилади. Геодезистлар инженерлик иншоотларини геометрик шакли, ўлчами ва конструктив ўзига хослиги бўйича ажратади.*

Keywords: *Industrial buildings, energy structures, hydraulic structures, transport structures, communication structures, civilian housing, rare structures, plots, dams, hydraulic structures, deformation, subsidence, displacement, deflection of reservoirs, hydrotechnical leveling network.*

For using Engineering construction may be subdivided into:

1. Industrial constructions (works, plants, factories);
2. Energy objects (thermal and nuclear power plants, heat power centers);
3. Transport structures (automobile and railways, bridges, ports, airports, transmission lines and pipelines);
4. Communication structures (antenna systems, communication systems and others);
5. Residential buildings (living, administrative, public buildings and objects);
6. Rare structures (charged particle accelerators, large radio telescopes, solar furnaces and power plants, high towers, towers and others);
7. Hydraulic structures (plots, hydroelectric plants, hydroelectric stations and others).

Examples of geometric shaped structures include residential areas, industrial plants, hydroelectric plants, thermal and nuclear power plants, solar ovens.

Linear structures: automobile and railways, canals, power lines, communication lines, pipelines

Buildings are divided by size: small (local), medium (district and regional significance), large (republican).

Industrial constructions Examples are industrial constructions – factories, plants, works which are built in cities and towns.

Chemical plants must have sanitary zones that separate them from the population.

Industrial enter-prises are divided into extractive and processing industries.

The structure of extractive industries includes coal, metal ores, non-ferrous metals, mineral fertilizers, construction materials and other industries. Extraction can be carried out in open and closed ways.

Enterprises in the manufacturing industry include machinery, metalworking, instrumentation, chemical, construction, light industry, food industry, medical and many others.

Residential, administrative and public buildings. Residential and administrative buildings are divided into floors: low (up to 5 floors), medium (5-12 floors) and high (12 floors). Nowadays, modern construction is building a high-rise.

Construction of public buildings occupies large areas. Schools, kindergar-tens, lyceums and colleges, as well as the standard houses currently under construction, are being built on standard design.

Transport and communication structures. The main transport networks are railways, highways, airways, waterways, main pipelines and others.

Railways. The first railroad was built in Russia in 1838 from Petersburg to Pavlovsky. Railways turns are defined within a radius of 150m, 180m, 200, 250 ... 4000 meters.

Airports. Airports are the main air transport structure and are divided into international, republic and local types and are used for passen-ger transportation.

Pipeline transport. Pipeline transport is able to carry cargo without a container or shelf. Oil, oil products, gas and water are the main cargoes for pipelines.

Communication structures. Examples of communications include telephone, radio, and space communications. Radio broadcasting sys-tems are among the most responsible communica-tion facilities. The tallest TV tower in the world – Toronto – 553m, Ostankino - 540m

When choosing a site for the construction of such facilities, special attention is paid to the study of soil composition, wind effects and seismic conditions of the area.

Rare structures. Rare structures are different but interconnected, large radio telescopes, telescopes, high temperature helicopters, industrial conveyor lines. Tower structures are one of the most complex engineering facilities to be built and used in difficult conditions.

Tower structures the main difference between the minaret structures and the industrial, residential and administrative buildings are:

1. The height of a building is much larger than its base size.
2. The technological device is weighed against the weight of the design.
3. The impact of design weight and weight on technological equipment is of secondary importance to wind impact.

Some radio tower structures are listed as rare buildings. Typically, such buildings are built in large cities, so they have high architectural requirements. These facilities include Eiffel in Paris, Ostankino in Moscow, Toronto in Canada, Kiev and Tashkent.

Solar ovens. The main task of high-temperature solar furnaces is to collect a certain amount of solar energy and to store it in a small area.

Hydraulic structures. The hydraulic structures will be built for the use of river energy, shipbuilding and timber drainage, water supply to residential and industrial enterprises, irrigation of fields, removal of used and collected water. Hydraulic structures include plots and dams, pipelines, mines and drainage structures, coastal structures. Plots are a dam blocker that holds water at different levels. They are built to generate electricity from hydroelectric power stations.

Deformation, subsidence, displacement and deflection of hydraulic structures have been observed for many years. Hydraulic structures can change over time due to subsidence or deflection in a vertical or horizontal plane for a variety of reasons. Deformation can occur during construction or during use after construction is complete. Deformation monitoring is carried out from time to time, depending on the type of structure and the nature of the change. For this purpose, a special area will be allocated near the facility, where a rapper and strong signs will be installed.

A geodetic marker that is mounted on the ground for a long time by a special device is called a geodetic marker (rapper). The word rapper is derived from the French (repère), which in geodesy means a sign, a target, a starting point.

Deformation values are calculated based on the results of two periods. Geodetic observations are carried out in March-April of the first period, ie when the maximum volume of water in the reservoir rises, and the second period of observations is carried out in October-November, when the volume of water in the reservoir decreases to a minimum. An analysis of the results of the two periods will determine how much the structure has sunk.

The horizontal displacement of hydraulic structures is determined by its points. Leveling of sinkholes will be carried out on the shore of the building. The appearance of the reservoir is analyzed twice a year based on measurement results. Geodetic observation of the subsidence and horizontal displacement of the reservoir is considered in accordance with the rules of technical operation. The development of a method for detecting deformation is of more scientific and industrial importance.

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